

THE ROLE OF TEACHING VOCABULARY FOR B1 LEVEL STUDENTS.

Miyasar Azatbaeva Satbaevna

Master's student at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Abstract: This article deals with the role of teaching vocabulary to B1 level English language learners. It will prove that teaching vocabulary is a creative endeavor, educators can develop their own special methods or techniques for doing so in accordance with their circumstances and skills at the time.

Key words: technology, vocabulary, help, improve, pay attention, expect, class, translate, sentence, level, comprehend.

It can be challenging to teach vocabulary to students at the intermediate (B1) level because their concentration spans are shorter than their motivation levels. Candidates for ESL learning at the B1 level (i.e., advanced independent users of the target language) are expected to comprehend the main idea of direct, everyday criticism on topics they encounter daily at work, in school, etc. Additionally, they must be able to handle the majority of situations that are likely to arise when they use objective language at home or overseas, in a variety of social settings. They can write a clear, comprehensible book on topics of personal or public interest, and they can describe experiences, occasions, goals, expectations, and aspirations while briefly providing justifications and explanations for ideas and goals.

The demand for specialists who are fluent in obscure dialects is growing steadily in our modern republic. Particularly, English is considered to be one of

the most difficult languages we use today. The fact that there is an emphasis on the English language in the showing is obviously anything but a mystery. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, signed a Decree "On measures to improve the learning arrangement of international languages, exactly English as a foreign language also to create a youthful generation that was contentedly growing, profoundly educated, and forward-thinking. Instead of focusing on teaching just a language, it is the most important aim to improve critical thinking, broaden pupils' horizons.

A word used in different contexts may have different connotations, so simply learning a word's definition without examples of where and when the word is used won't help students fully comprehend its significance. It is challenging for students to use the words in spoken and written language when they are forced to memorize a list of terms without any reference to the context.

The best method to acquire vocabulary and understand how a word's meaning relates to the words around which it appears to be to look at the context in which the word appears. Additionally, a definition-incorporating technique can produce comprehensive and adaptable information on word implications, just like its use in the content.

Students start to understand how a word's meaning can change and shift based on its context when they are given multiple sentences that use the same word in various ways. Words must be seen in various situations for learners to fully understand them.

Because students become more preoccupied with specific items and less conscious of the context, which provides them with meaning, too much dictionary work can kill all interest in reading and even interfere with comprehension. Additionally, it causes all sluggish and ineffective reading.

When it comes to teaching English vocabulary, nothing beats the grammatical translation technique, which dates back to the 1500s. There are two approaches: reciting grammatical rules and translating sentences. Teaching

English vocabulary comes second to reading classical literature when the goal is to learn vocabulary. Listening and speaking do not help to solidify the language that is read aloud in class. Flouting has been a direct technique since the late 1800s. The direct approach requires that each phrase be listened to and the student's handwriting reviewed afterward. In light of the shortcomings of the direct approach, several British and American academics started to adopt more contemporary strategies for learning languages

Vocabulary instruction must, in fact, be meaningful to pupils. This happens when a student is able to connect new words to his or her previous knowledge or conceptual framework. According to Pearson and Spiro, a schema is a mental image or link you create after reading a word or sentence.

What does the term "know" actually mean?

- understanding its various meanings.
- being aware of the part of speech (a noun, a verb, etc.)
- being able to articulate it clearly;
- being able to incorporate it into a sentence in the right grammatical structure.
- being able to distinguish between various types of English, such as boot/trunk and lift/elevator [British/American].

Learners must at the very least understand both the form and the meaning of a new term. It's important to note that for a word to have a tight meaning-to-form fit, both of these facets should be displayed simultaneously. The less likely it is that a learner will mentally link a word's form and meaning, the bigger the gap between the two is presented. Let's assume the teacher has chosen to teach a collection of words that are related, such as clothing items, like shirts, pants, jackets, socks, dresses, and jeans.

An obvious option when presenting a group of concrete objects, such as clothing items, is to illustrate or demonstrate them as an alternative to translation. This can be accomplished by miming, using actual objects (also known as realia), or by using pictures. One method that distinguished the Direct Method was the use of

realia, pictures, and demonstration. A response to such highly intellectual approaches to language acquisition as Grammar-Translation was the development of the Direct Method, which forgoes the use of translation.

There are many different types of visual aids, including board drawings, wall charts, transparencies displayed using an overhead projector on the board or wall, and published and homemade flashcards. Many educators create their own collections of flashcards using materials like calendars and magazines.

Pictures of things from the following sets are particularly helpful: food and drink, clothing, house interiors, and furnishings, landscapes, and exteriors, modes of transportation, as well as a large selection of pictures of people, split into sets like professions, nationalities, sports, etc.

It is preferable that this mental representation be accurate because learners are likely to create a mental image of the likely spelling of new words as soon as they first hear them. However, there is a much more significant cause to begin using written language right away. Important hints to meaning are frequently much simpler to spot in written form than in spoken form. In speaking, sounds frequently blend together or are even dropped completely, causing words like a handbag to sound like hambag and police station to sound like a flee station, even when carefully crafted.

To conclude, it can be proven that while teaching vocabulary it is important to pay close attention to every single part, including pronunciation, meaning, usage, and collocation forms. Since the step of usage of those given words is more essential than just memorizing them.

References

- Hapsari A. Language Learning Strategies in English Language Learning: A Survey Study. *Ling Pedagog J English Teach Stud.* 2019;1
- VanDeWeghe R. What about Vocabulary Instruction? *English J.* 2007;97
- Treffers-Daller J. Vocabulary and reading. In: *Vocabulary and the Four Skills.*

2020.

McGuinness D. Vocabulary and Reading. In: Language Development and Learning to Read. 2018